

Synthesis and Characterization of some Metal Ion Complexes with 8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-4-chloro/nitroaniline

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The Schiff base compounds of 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin with substituted aromatic amines, viz. 4-chloroaniline and 4-nitroaniline have been synthesized and their metal complexes with Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{II} have been prepared. The Schiff bases function as bidentate anionic ligands chelating through deprotonated phenolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen. The ligand field parameters of the complexes have been evaluated.

Schiff base metal complexes have been widely studied because of their industrial and biological applications¹. Not much work has been done on the Schiff base complexes of substituted coumarins. The derivatives of such compounds as such and also after suitable structural modifications may be used as drugs^{2,3}.

The present investigation aims at the study of the complexes of life-essential metal ions with such bioactive ligands in order to work out systematically their structural and biological significance.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complexes (Table 1) of 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-4-chloro/nitroaniline indicate metal-ligand stoichiometry for all the complexes to be 1 : 2. The conductivity data in DMF ($10^{-3}M$) confirm their non-electrolytic nature ($10-30 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)⁴. The observed magnetic moment values for the 8-acetyl-7-hy-

droxy-4-methylcoumarin-4-chloroaniline (ACCA)- Co^{II} and - Ni^{II} complexes suggest an octahedral geometry while that for the Cu^{II} complex a square-planar geometry. The magnetic moment data of 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-4-nitroaniline (ACNA)-metal complexes suggest an octahedral geometry for the Co^{II} and square-planar for the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes^{6,7}.

The ir ligand (Schiff base) band at $3300-3350 \text{cm}^{-1}$, disappears in the metal complexes suggesting the deprotonation of phenolic-OH after coordination through phenolic oxygen. The C-O(phenolic) band observed at $1210-1220 \text{cm}^{-1}$ in the ligand shows a positive shift in the complexes ($1240 \pm 10 \text{cm}^{-1}$), confirming the involvement of deprotonated phenolic oxygen on complexation. The shifting of the ligand band at $1600-1610 \text{cm}^{-1}$ to lower side at 1570 ± 10 in the complexes suggests the participation of C=N (azomethine) group in chelation. The band at $1720-1730 \text{cm}^{-1}$ due to C=O coumarin in the ligand spectrum remains almost unaltered ($\pm 5 \text{cm}^{-1}$) in the complexes, thus ruling out its participation on coordination. The presence of water molecules in the coordination sphere of Co^{II} -ACCA, Ni^{II} -ACCA and Co^{II} -ACNA complexes has been inferred by the presence of characteristic bands at 3450 ± 20 and $830 \pm 10 \text{cm}^{-1}$. The new bands in the spectra of the complexes around 415 ± 10 and $510 \pm 20 \text{cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to M-O and M-N bonding respectively^{3,5,6}.

The electronic spectrum of Co^{II} -ACCA complex shows bands at 10.50, 18.90, 19.95 and 21.80 kK, corresponding to transitions ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$, ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2T_{1g}$, ${}^2T_{2g}$, ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(\text{F})$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(\text{P})$ respectively. The lowest and highest energy bands can, therefore, be assigned to ν_1 and ν_3 transitions and the shoulders may be considered to have arisen due to splitting of ν_3 or ν_2 transition. The values of $10Dq$, B , β , ν_3/ν_2 and LFSE are 13125cm^{-1} , 0.28cm^{-1} , 0.82 , 1.09 and $125.68 \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$ respectively, which are in conformity with the octahedral geometry. In Co^{II} -ACNA complex, the bands characteristic to ν_2 and ν_3 transitions appear at 15.32 and 20.40 kK. The ν_1 transition

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Molecular formula Compd./ (Colour)	M.p./Dec. ($\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$)	Metal%: Found/ (Calcd.)	Mag. mom. B.M.
$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClNO}_3$ (Yellow)	152	-	-
$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{ClNO}_3)_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Violet)	218	7.6 (7.0)	4.98
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{ClNO}_3)_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Brown)	212	7.6 (7.3)	3.01
$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{ClNO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Brown)	195	7.8 (8.1)	1.92
$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$ (ligand) (Yellow)	178	-	-
$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Brown)	229	7.4 (7.8)	4.9
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Orange)	217	7.6 (7.3)	Diam.
$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Brown)	192	8.1 (8.4)	1.99

*All compounds gave satisfactory C,H and N analyses; ACCA = $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClNO}_3$, ACNA = $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$.

band could not be clearly recorded. The values of ligand field parameters, viz. $10Dq$, B , β , ν_3/ν_2 and LFSE are 8512 cm^{-1} , 1019 cm^{-1} , 0.90 , 1.33 and 81.51 kJ mol^{-1} respectively, which are in fair agreement with the predicted values of octahedral complex^{6,7}.

In Ni^{II} -ACCA complex, the bands appearing at 14.50 and 24.80 kK , are assignable to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g(\text{F})}(\nu_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g(\text{F})} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g(\text{P})}(\nu_3)$ respectively. The first band due to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(\nu_1)$ has been found missing. An octahedral geometry has tentatively been suggested for this complex. The spectrum of Ni^{II} -ACNA complex shows bands at 18.46 and 27.30 kK corresponding to transitions ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}(\nu_2)$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}(\nu_3)$. The first band ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g(\nu_1)$ is weaker. A square-planar geometry has been suggested for this complex⁷.

In the spectrum of Cu^{II} -ACCA complex, the bands at 14.20 and 16.60 kK have been assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ respectively. The similar bands have also been observed in the electronic spectrum of Cu^{II} -ACNA complex at 12.30 and 15.10 kK . This supports the square-planar geometry for both the Cu^{II} complexes^{6,7}.

Magnetic data for all these complexes substantiate the same view for stereoarrangements.

Experimental

8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin was synthesized by the reported procedure³. The Schiff bases (ligands) were synthesized by refluxing equimolar amounts of 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin and 4-chloro/nitroaniline in methanolic medium on a water-bath for ~ 6 h. The resulting product was of yellow color.

The metal complex was prepared by refluxing a mix-

ture of methanolic solutions of the metal salt $\text{MSO}_4 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.01 mol) and 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-4-chloroaniline/nitroaniline (0.02 mol) on a water-bath for $6-8$ h. The colored precipitate that appeared on cooling the solution, was dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl_2 and also in an electric oven at 80° .

References

1. E. SINN and C. H. HARRIS, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1969, **4**, 391; A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 357; M. N. HUGHES, "Inorganic Chemistry of Biological Processes", Wiley, New York, 1981.
2. A. P. MISHRA, V. SRIVASTAVA, and S. K. SRIVASTAVA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1995, **25**, 21; D. K. RASTOGI, A. K. SRIVASTAVA, P. C. JAIN, and B. R. AGRAWAL, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1972, **6**, 145; Y. MAEDA, Y. TAKASHINA, and Y. NISHIDA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.* 1976, **49**, 2427.
3. P. V. RAO, N. R. RAO, V. J. T. RAJU, and M. C. GANORKAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 482; G. P. POKHARIYAL and P. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 501; P. SHARAN, S. GIRI, and NIZZAMUDDIN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 393.
4. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
5. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 4th. ed., Wiley, New York, 1986; R. M. SILVERSTEIN, G. C. BASSLER, and T. C. MORRILL, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", 4th. ed., New York, 1981.
6. A. P. MISHRA, S. K. SRIVASTAVA, and V. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **73**, 261; 1997, **74**, 487.
7. R. L. DUTTA and A. SYAMAL, "Elements of Magnetochemistry", 2nd. ed., Afflt. East-West Press, New Delhi, 1993; A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd. ed., Elsevier Amsterdam, 1984; B. N. FIGGIS in "Comprehensive Coordination Chemistry", ed. G. WILKINSON, Pergamon, New York, 1977, Vol. 2, p. 214.